

The Comparison of Thai Tourists Behaviors In Services Qualification Thai Boarding Point : Case Study of Thai- Lao Bridge, Nongkhai and Nakorn Panom.

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ABSTRACT: The abstract should summarize the content of the paper. to compare qualification of border services between Nongkhai Border (NB) and Nakhon Phanom Border (NPB). The questionnaire was used as a main research instrument. It was used to collect the data on the perception of the 770 samples. The samples are all Thai tourists and use border services from both Nongkhai Border (385) and Nakhon Phanom Border (385). The convenience sampling was used a main method of data analysis. The collected data was analysed by using statistical package. Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, and ANOVA (i.e. t-test, F-test) were also used to analyse the collected data. It is suggested that the tourists who had different ages, education background, monthly income, and different purposes in travelling showed no difference at 0.05 in statistical difference in border service use in Nakhon Phanom Border. However, the factors i.e. age and occupation within the same group showed statistical difference at 0.05 in border service use in Nakhon Phanom Border.

KEYWORDS - Thai Tourists, services qualification , Thai boarding point , Thai- Lao Bridge.

I. INTRODUCTION

Thailand and the Lao People's Democratic Republic's borders have been connected for a long time. It has been known that the two countries have been joining 'trade' and 'travel' for long time. It has also has an effect on transportation between these two countries and has been considered as 'Thai-Lao as neighbour' and have good relationships for long time including geography, society, culture and language, politic and economy, especially the transportation between Thai and Lao, travelling. Besides, with a 'history' that has been developed for long time, and with the closeness of Thailand and Lao. Their borders have been connected approximately 1.810 kilometres, and been connected to 11 provinces: Nong Khai, Mukdahan, Ubonrachathani, Nakhon Phanom, Loei, Nan, Phayao, Utaradit, Chaiangrai, Pitsanulok, and Umnartcharoen. It has passed through 'border trade' in 36 points as they are called '36 permanent border service point', 2 temporary border service points', and 20 negotiating points. The transportation from Thailand to Lao can be done by private car, train, or transportation cars. Thus, there is a potential for many Thai tourists to travel in Lao. This is also supported by Thailand and Lao governments, in particular 'transportation business between Thailand and Lao[1].

The people from the Greater Mekong Sub-region (GMS) countries such as Myanmar, Thailand, Cambodia, the People Republic of China, the Lao People's Democratic Republic and Vietnam are 240 million. They have their own identities in their society, and culture. From this reason, it has attracted the people to travel in GMS. In 1992, GMS countries have been offered helped from Asian Development Bank (ADB) to be able to cooperate in economic with the Greater Mekong Sub-region (GMS) [2].

As above reasons, countries in this region tend to expand more trades into the region such as the Indonesia Malaysia Thailand Growth Triangle or IMT-GT, Great Mekong Basin Region or GSM comprising of

6 countries including China, Thailand, Myanmar, Vietnam, Laos and Cambodia. These economic cooperative groups have cooperated in trades, investments and transportation connection. Thailand has benefited from these kinds of cooperation to expand trade into the region as well as expanding tourism industry in the provinces along the inter-connected transportation routes[3]. Thailand is geographical center of South East Asia as it has borders with neighboring countries. Thailand can trade with 4 neighboring countries including Myanmar, Laos, Malaysia and Cambodia which share the border lines with 30 provinces of Thailand. This can enhance different forms of trade[4].

In term of tourism, these economic areas can attract tourists to experience the natures and the exotic cultures, which spot all over the provinces along Mekong River. These include nature, history, culture, tradition, life style of different ethnic groups. The rich resources will help promote Thailand becoming tourist hub of the region or becoming Indochina Gateway.

The other benefit of Thai government's open boarding point service of bordering provinces along Myanmar, Malaysia, Laos, and Cambodia is that it boosts tourism in the area. The number of tourists has increased. This encourages the Thai government to promote tourism in boarding points. As a result, Thailand has cooperated with Australia and Laos to construct the bridge across the longest river in South East Asia (about 4,000 km) in Nongkhai province[5]. This river flows through many countries including China, Myanmar, Laos, Thailand, Cambodia and Vietnam. It is the first bridge crossing Mekong River, connecting Thailand and Laos. The bridge is called Thai-Laos Friendship Bridge. The bridge connects the transportation from Nongkhai to Vientiane. Besides, Thailand has constructed the third bridge crossing Mekong River in Nakorn Panom, which connected Thailand with Kam Muan of Laos. The bridge enhances the traveling between Nongkhai and Nakorn Panom of Thailand and Kam Muan of Laos with comfort. As a result, it boosts Thai cargo transportation as well as tourism[6].

The geographical advantage of Nongkhai and Nakorn Panom as a gateway for trade, investment and tourism results in the changes in society, economy, trade, and tourism of both provinces. Moreover, the openness, political stability, natural resources of Laos supports the future forecast that there will be more development to support the economic and social growth as well as the growth in tourism. This will drive Thailand to become tourism hub in the Sub Mekong region or Indochina Gateway. These promising situations encouraged the researcher to conduct the research of The Comparison of Thai Tourists behaviors in services qualification Thai boarding point : Case study of Thai- Lao Bridge, Nongkhai and Nakorn Panom. The research aims to compare the tourist behavior in choosing boarding point services. The study result would identify the motivation, attitudes and behaviors which could be useful in tourism strategy to increase number of tourists in the provinces that have boarding point. The result of the study could be used to improve the service quality of the boarding points to meet the needs and satisfaction of tourists.

II. OBJECTIVES/RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To compare qualification of border services between Nongkhai Border (NB) and Nakhon Phanom Border (NPB).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The questionnaire was used as a main research instrument. It was used to collect the data on the perception of the 770 samples. The samples are all Thai tourists and use border services from both Nongkhai Border (385) and Nakhon Phanom Border (385).

The convenience sampling was used a main method of data analysis. The collected data was analysed by using statistical package. Frequency, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, and ANOVA (i.e. t-test, F-test) were also used to analyse the collected data.

IV. FINDINGS

Summary results according to the research hypothesis

Nakorn Panom boarding point

1.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different genders in terms of response, understanding, tangibility have no differences with significant statistic at 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different genders in terms of trust and guarantee are different with significant statistic at 0.05

2.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different ages in terms of response, guarantee, and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic at 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different ages in terms of trust and understanding are different with significant statistic at 0.05

3.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different education backgrounds in all aspects are different with significant statistic of 0.05

4.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different average incomes in terms of understanding, guarantee and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different average incomes in terms of trust and response are different with significant statistic of 0.05

5.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different careers in terms of response and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different careers in terms of trust, understanding and guarantee are different with significant statistic of 0.05

6.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different traveling objectives in terms of response, understanding, and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom of tourists with different traveling objectives in terms of trust and guarantee are different with significant statistic at 0.05

Nongkhai boarding point

1.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different genders in terms of trust, understanding, tangibility and guarantee have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different genders in terms of response are different with significant statistic of 0.05.

2.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different ages in terms of trust, guarantee, and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different ages in terms of response and understanding are different with significant statistic of 0.05

3.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different education backgrounds in terms of trust, response and guarantee have no difference with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different education backgrounds in terms of understanding and tangibility are different with significant statistic of 0.05.

4.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different average incomes in terms of guarantee and trust have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different average incomes in terms of response, understanding and tangibility are different with significant statistic of 0.05

5.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different careers in terms of trust and tangibility have no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different careers in terms of response, understanding and guarantee are different with significant statistic of 0.05

6.The behaviors in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different traveling objectives in terms of response and guarantee has no differences with significant statistic of 0.05. The behaviors in

choosing boarding point in Nongkhai of tourists with different traveling objectives in terms of trust, understanding and tangibility are different with significant statistic at 0.05. To ensure a high-quality product, diagrams and lettering MUST be either computer-drafted or drawn using India ink.

V. CONCLUSION

1. Comparison of Thai tourist opinion on service quality of Thai boarding point : Case study of Thai-Lao friendship bridge in Nakorn Panom with different ages, genders, educations, average incomes, careers and traveling objectives.

Tourists with different genders, educations, average incomes and traveling objectives have no behavioral difference in choosing boarding point in Nakorn Panom, with significant statistic of 0.05. The results are in line with the study of [7][8] who studied the guidelines for potential and strategy development of service quality of Taksila Hotel, Tambol Talad, Mahasarakam province. He found that the hotel's clients with different ages, genders, educations, and incomes have the similar opinion on service quality of the hotel with significant statistic of 0.05.

2. Comparison of Thai tourist opinion on service quality of Thai boarding point : Case study of Thai-Lao friendship bridge in Nongkhai with different ages, genders, educations, average incomes, careers and traveling objectives.

Tourists with different genders, educations, average incomes and traveling objectives have no behavioral difference in choosing boarding point in Nongkhai, with significant statistic of 0.05. The results are in line with the study of [9][10] who studied the guidelines for potential and strategy development of service quality of Taksila Hotel, Tambol Talad, Mahasarakam province. He found that the hotel's clients with different ages, genders, educations, and incomes have the similar opinion on service quality of the hotel with significant statistic of 0.05.

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